

**КИЧИК ГУРУҲЛАРНИ ЎРГАНИШ ПСИХОЛОГИК МУАММО
СИФАТИДА**

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Аннотация: Мақолада кичик гуруҳларга турли хил индивидуал имкониятларнинг рўёбга чиқариш, расмий ва норасмий гуруҳлар доирасидаги ўқувчилар жамоасида ўзига хос ижтимоий психологик хусусиятларнинг қанчалик муҳим эклиги хусусида фикр мулоҳазалар юритилган.

Калит сўзлар: кичик гуруҳ, расмий ва норасмий гуруҳлар, ижтимоий перцепция, педагогик жараён, тарбиявий муносабатлар, таълим, тарбия, ўзини-ўзи тарбиялаш, мулоқот ва ривожланиш.

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SMALL GROUP STUDY AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM.

Abstract: The article discusses the realization of various individual opportunities in small groups, the importance of specific social psychological characteristics in the student body within formal and informal groups.

Key words: small group, formal and informal groups, social perception, pedagogical process, educational relations, education, training, self-education, communication and development.

Enter. It is known that in the science of social psychology, although there is not enough scientific literature dedicated to the problem of providing

psychological services to small groups and able to describe all its directions in detail, today in the world of science and the development of society, there are scientific studies that can show the necessity of the problem of psychological services and justify its "methodological roots". can be noted separately. In the analysis of the literature, it is important to research some general aspects related to the methodology of psychological services from the point of view of social psychology.

For example, all researchers, following the methodological principles of social psychology, theoretically and scientifically substantiate this or that aspect important for psychological services. Among them, there are studies aimed at identifying social psychological tasks that are of great theoretical and scientific importance for the successful organization of psychological services (Andreeva G.M. Davletshin M.G., Zabrodin Yu.M., Carnegi D., Karimova V.M., Parigin (Abulkhanova-Slavskaya K.A., Anufriev E.A., Grimak L.P., Lomov B.F., Leytes N.S., Golubeva E.A., Kadyrov B.R.), Lipkina A.I. ,Petrovsky V.A., Rubinstein S.L., Kadyrov B.R.; research related to the formation of social institutions in small groups (Asmolv A.G., Nadirashvili Sh.A., Uznadze D.N., Shikhirev P.N., Allpoqt G.W.); research related to group activity motivational urges and activity satisfaction (Bojovich L.I., Bratko A.A., Vilyunas V.K., Dodonov B.I., Kitwell T.A. Maslow A.H.); research related to the provision of an individual approach to a person in the context of small groups (Klimov E.A., Merlin B.S., Nebilitsyn V.D., Peysakhov N.M., Rusalov V.M., Slavina L.S., Strelyau A. , Teplov B.M.); researches devoted to the perspectives of the approach based on the personality system (Zdravomislov A.G., Kuzmin E.S., Lazursky A.F., Muksinov R.I., Myasishchev V.N., Stolin V.V, shcherbakov A.I., Bogoslavsky V.V.); studies investigating perspectives of the approach to the individual based on emotional-will qualities (Bassin F.V., Vasilyuk F.E., Gissen L.D., Zilberman P.B., Konopkin O.A., Majidov N., Naenko N.I. , Prihojan A.M., Rozelnblat V.V., Heckhausen H., Eberlein G., Nevv D.O.); research devoted to the research of the psychological

service program in educational institutions (Breinstein M.S., Dubrovina I.V., Kala U.V., Rudik V.V., Leimets H.O., Mattes G.O., Pratuivich Yu.M. , Sierd Yu.L.) and, finally, research aimed at substantiating important aspects of psychological service in the organization of family life (M.Argoy, Bodalev A.A., Stolin V.V., Karimova V.M., Kovalev S.V. , Soginov N.A., Shoumarov G'.B.) can be noted separately. We think that this will help to think about some current aspects, problems and their solutions related to the provision of psychological services to small groups as a theoretical-scientific and methodological resource to think about and define the tasks of our own research. Because "unity of person and activity", "development of consciousness in activity", "treatment", "individual approach", "attitude", "lifestyle", "social establishment", "objective existence" which are the main criteria of all social psychological principles created to date and subjective reflection", "community", "social satisfaction", "social behavior" and the practical role and perspective in society cannot be fully imagined without the application of psychological services. exposure of the problem of approach requires a more serious thinking and reflection about the methodology of psychological service.

It is impossible to separate the practical psychology of a person, related to the traditions of the development of today's psychological science, from his social activity and social nature in society. From this point of view, the process of correct and effective management of human factors and its social processes in society requires the inevitability of providing psychological services to society and its members. Consequently, the development of each science is directly related to the structure of methodological devices that reveal the scientific direction based on new evidence. Because there will be no clear practical results in the field without clear methodology. After all, another important new task of the science of social psychology is the analysis of how to determine the scope of theoretical, practical and empirical research related to the methodology of psychological services. In this regard, it is clear that the world of psychology has not yet adopted a single scientific direction or concept that has been clearly and perfectly developed and

officially recognized (perhaps it is not possible because the scientific and psychological views of scientists are different), representatives of advanced western psychology, including the central There are studies that have been carried out and are carried out by psychologists from the Commonwealth of Nations and psychologists from Uzbekistan, which have a unique authority and influence for the world of science, which can serve as a basis for forming our scientific and practical ideas about the psychological service program and social prospects. As we know from the scientific literature, the general directions of social psychological service methodology are expressed. The researches of representatives of Western social psychology can be explained as follows: W. Wundt's large (ten-volume) epic work entitled "Psychology of Nations" published in 1900 served to highlight the directions of social psychology and revealed the complex aspects of studying human spirituality, culture and ideology. The theory of "social instincts of behavior" written in 1908 by the famous English psychologist William McDougall "Introduction to Social Psychology" served as the first basis for elucidating the problem of ensuring the harmony of human instincts and activities, as opposed to Freudianism.

Consequently, scientists such as E. Fromm, J. Sullivan, V. Shutts, G. Sheparde, and V. Bayon laid the foundation for the creation of the theory of group psychology. In this case, the first demonstration of the ways to improve the psychological climate related to interpersonal relations in a group with various social psychological trainings can serve as a certain level of empirical information for defining social psychological service tasks in work teams. Theories within the framework of cognitivism created in the West are important for the methodology of psychological services. For example, L. Festinger's theory of cognitive dissonance (based on the conscious change of a person's behavior or attitude towards the object of activity), T. Newhom's cooperative communicative theory (based on the formation of positive relationships with others and the common object of activity), Ch. Osgood and P. Tanenbaum theory of "congruence" (aimed

at evaluating an object based on human cognitive structure), G. Allport, A. These include a number of humanistic researches by social psychologists such as Maslau and K. Rogers. It should also be noted that the famous American psychologist Abraham Harold Maslau's "concept of a holistic approach to a person" is of great importance for research on the problem of understanding and social motivational development of a person in the process of psychological service. According to Maslau, all the innate potential of a person can be realized and mature only with the creation of social conditions. Of course, the truth of these thoughts is confirmed by the results of our regular observations of the organization of psychological service, whose main task is to study and educate the scope of each person's unique and social development capabilities.

In general, it is observed that the theoretical and methodological roots of providing psychological support to small groups, which is a certain part of psychological service, are followed by the tendency of assessment by the scientists of different groups with the psychological provision of harmony of personality and activity.

Summary and suggestions. In general, summarizing the above theoretical analysis, we can come to the following conclusions regarding the coverage of this problem in scientific literature.

In Western psychology, the problem of small groups is central to the constant communication of respondents, the cooperative actions of a small group of individuals, the understanding of the quantitative differences of objects and subjects in each group based on mutual dyads, the formation of mutual perceptions related to the process of group identification, and the complex of scientific observations.

In Russian psychology, the problem of small groups is interpreted based on such circumstances as the emotionality, desire, needs and specific social orientation of the members of each group. In the center of these interpretations, the special communicative, interactive and perceptive aspects of this dialogue are the

power that moves small groups.

In today's advanced social psychology, it is possible to pay special attention to the existence of a tendency to solve the problem of small groups based on the results of experimental studies aimed at determining the process of identification in one or another group and its role in interaction and communication.

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